

Dual infection of plants with ragged stunt and other virus diseases

K. C. Ling, plant pathologist, E. R. Tiongco, senior research assistant, and V. M. Aguiero, research assistant, International Rice Research Institute

In the Philippines, there are five virus and virus-like diseases of rice plants – grassy stunt, orange leaf, ragged stunt, tungro, and yellow dwarf (orange leaf and yellow dwarf are of minor importance). Rice plants can be infected with both tungro and grassy stunt. Therefore, dual infection of ragged stunt and grassy stunt or ragged stunt and tungro was studied by inoculating seedlings of TN1 with the respective viruliferous insects in the greenhouse.

Rice plants were infected with both grassy stunt and ragged stunt (Fig. 1, 2). The dually infected plants had the symptoms of both grassy stunt (profuse tillering and narrow leaf blades) and ragged stunt (ragged leaves). They were much more stunted, particularly at later growth stages. The tips of some leaves were twisted.

Rice plants were also infected with both tungro and ragged stunt (Fig. 3). The infected plants showed stunting, yellowing of leaves (a tungro symptom), and ragged leaves (ragged stunt symptom).

1. A rice plant infected with both ragged stunt and grassy stunt.

2. Close-up of the dually infected plant, showing ragged leaves.

3. A rice plant infected with both ragged stunt and tungro.

The dual infection indicates absence of cross protection either between ragged stunt and grassy stunt or between ragged stunt and tungro. Hence, the causal agent of ragged stunt is not closely related to the causal agent of grassy stunt or of tungro. ❧

A study of vein-swellings of rice plants infected with ragged stunt

P. Q. Cabauatan, research aide, and K. C. Ling, plant pathologist, International Rice Research Institute

One symptom of rice ragged stunt disease is the appearance of narrow, elongated swellings of veins, a result of proliferation of phloem cells in vascular bundles.

Vein-swelling seems to be a more appropriate term than *gall* to describe that symptom. Galls have been defined as large swellings on plant tissues caused by the invasion of parasites such as fungi and bacteria, or as excrescences of plants caused by fungi, mites, or insects. The definitions imply that the causal agent or parasite is localized in or restricted to the galls. That does not hold true for malformations due to the systemic

infection of a virus, because the virus also spreads to other plant parts. Therefore, it has been suggested that virus-induced abnormalities be classified as enations or tumors rather than as galls. For ragged stunt disease, vein-swelling is preferred because it is both specific and descriptive.

When 60 rice varieties and lines that had been naturally infected with ragged stunt were examined at or after the late tillering stage, all had vein-swellings. Of the 170 diseased hills examined, 96% had vein-swellings. Not every diseased hill of some rices had vein-swellings. For instance, only about 50% of diseased hills of Raminad strain 3 had them. Nor did every tiller in a diseased hill have vein-swellings. Of the 794 tillers of diseased plants of 18 rices examined, 66% had

them. The percentage of tillers with vein-swellings seemed to increase as the plants grew older.

The vein-swellings appeared on leaf sheaths, blades, and culms at varying frequencies. Of the 1,006 vein swellings examined, 72% appeared on the leaf sheath, 21% on the blades, and 7% on the culms. The vein-swellings were not distributed evenly on the leaf sheaths, nor on the blades. About 90% of those on the leaf sheaths appeared on the upper half. About 60% of those on the leaf blades were on the lower half, most near the collar.

The vein-swellings were on the outer surfaces of leaf sheaths or on the lower surfaces of blades. None were observed on the opposite sides, possibly because of the location of phloem cells in the tissue

and of the swelling due to their proliferation.

The vein-swollings varied in width from 0.2 to about 1 mm, and in length from about 1 mm to more than 10 cm. The number varied among tillers and varieties. The average was 4.3 vein-swollings/tiller among the 794 tillers of 42 diseased hills of 18 rices examined.

Of the 1,099 vein-swollings examined, 82% were white or pale yellow; 2%, light brown; 6%, dark brown; and 10%, mixed (one portion pale yellow, the other, brown). The colors seemed to remain unchanged until the death of the rice plants.

The vein-swollings appeared on both leaf sheaths and blades of artificially

infected plants at about 3 weeks after inoculation.

Although vein-swollings are less conspicuous than other symptoms of ragged stunt disease – ragged or twisted leaves and malformed or twisted flag leaves – they appeared fairly consistently on the diseased plants, particularly during later growth. ❧

A new medium for multiplication of sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* (*Thanatephorus cucumeris*)

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar 608101, Tamil Nadu, India

A new rice sand medium was developed for multiplication of *R. solani* to infect rice through soil inoculation at the seedling stage. Two hundred grams of well-sieved river sand was put in 250-ml Erlenmeyer flasks and 40 ml of tap water was added. Rice grains at 1 to 5% levels were added, sterilized at 15 psi for 1 hour, and inoculated with a single *R. solani* sclerotium. The incorporation of rice grains at 5% level was optimum to obtain maximum mycelial growth and sclerotial production. By the 7th day maximum mycelial growth and sclerotial production had been attained. The rice sand medium was used at an inoculum level of 25% to artificially induce rice seedling infection. ❧

Relationships involved in the bacterial blight syndrome

T. W. Mew, associate plant pathologist, International Rice Research Institute

The bacterial blight syndrome in the tropics has three types of symptoms: leaf blight, kresek, and pale yellow symptoms. The kresek and leaf blight symptoms are distinct and independent of each other (i.e. individual plants may be infected by either kresek or leaf blight). The kresek-infected plants may serve as a

source of inoculum for secondary infection leading to leaf blight, while leaf blight infection may turn into kresek if plants are infected during early growth or if the variety is susceptible to bacterial

Seed-borne nature of sheath blight pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* in rice

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar 608101, Tamil Nadu, India

Seed of the variety ADT 31, which is susceptible to sheath blight disease, were collected from a crop affected by sheath blight during 1975 kuruvai (June-Sept), 1975-76 thaladi (Oct-Jan), and 1976 navarai (Feb-May), and tested for the presence of *R. solani*. The presence of the pathogen in seed planted in Dixon Agar medium indicated its seed-borne nature. Isolation of the fungus from seeds ranged from 4 to 6.6%. Seed collected in the thaladi had the highest infection (6.6%) followed by those in navarai (5%) and kuruvai (4%). ❧

Effect of different soil types on rice seedling infection caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*

S. Kannaiyan and N. N. Prasad, Microbiology Laboratory, Agriculture College, Annamalai University, Annamalai nagar 608101, Tamil Nadu, India

Seedlings of ADT 31, which is susceptible to sheath blight infection caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, were raised in pots

filled with soils of various types: red, clay, sandy loam, laterite, alluvial, black, and sandy. The sheath blight pathogen was multiplied in a rice sand medium and inoculated at the 25% level. Seedling infection was less in sandy soil (29.3%) and black soil (40%). The maximum seedling infection was recorded in clay soil (78.6%) followed by that in red, alluvial, laterite, and sandy loam soils. ❧

Preliminary observations of brown spot and its control in rice in Peru

Alberto Jimenez S., Carlos Panizo S., Victorio Garcia V., and Jose Senmache S., Lambayeque, Peru

During the 1976-77 rice season severe brown spot symptoms, similar to those caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae*, were observed in the variety Nylamp planted at several sites in Lambayeque.

A fungus was isolated from diseased leaves. The mycelium was cream-colored and produced spore-like structures. The isolate failed to sporulate in a medium that was appropriate for *H. oryzae*.

From the nature of lesions and the failure of the mycelium to sporulate, the symptoms observed on Nylamp seem to have been caused by a fungus belonging to the *Dematracea* group, similar to *H. oryzae*. ❧